

**A REVIEW ARTICLE ON RAKTAKSHAYA DUE TO
SANTARPANJANYA AND APTARPANJANYA PANDUROGA WITH
SPECIAL REFERENCE TO IRON DEFICIENCY ANAEMIA**

Dr. Firoj Kumar*¹, Dr. Gitanjali Sasmal², Dr. Vinay Bhardwaj³

¹Post Graduate scholar, Department of Kriya Sharira, Shri NPA Govt. Ayurved College Raipur Chhattisgarh India.

²Professor & H.O.D. Department of Kriya Sharira, Shri NPA Govt. Ayurved College Raipur Chhattisgarh India.

³Reader Department of Kriya Sharira, Shri NPA Govt. Ayurved College Raipur Chhattisgarh India.

Article Received on 15 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 16 Dec. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17949215>

***Corresponding Author**

Dr. Firoj Kumar

Post Graduate Scholar, Department of
Kriya Sharira, Shri NPA Govt.
Ayurved College Raipur Chhattisgarh
India.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Firoj Kumar*¹, Dr. Gitanjali Sasmal², Dr. Vinay Bhardwaj³ (2025). A Review Article On Raktakshaya Due To Santarpanjanya And Aptarpanjanya Panduroga With Special Reference To Iron Deficiency Anaemia. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 389-399. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Raktakshaya, the depletion or qualitative deterioration of Rakta Dhatu, is a significant pathological condition described in Ayurvedic classics. It is a key manifestation of Pandu Roga, which clinically parallels iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) in modern medicine. According to Ayurvedic principles, Raktakshaya may occur due to either **Santarpanajanya** (over-nourishment) or **Aptarpanajanya** (under-nourishment) causes, each leading to distinct doshic imbalances. Santarpana contributes to Kapha-dominance and obstructs the normal dhatu-pachana (tissue metabolism), while Aptarpana results in weakened Agni and poor dhatu-nourishment, particularly affecting Rakta Dhatu. By comparing classical Ayurvedic texts with current scientific literature. In Ayurvedic literature, Raktakshaya refers to the deficiency or qualitative deterioration of Rakta Dhatu (blood tissue), resulting in systemic imbalances. One of the most common manifestations of Raktakshaya is Pandu Roga, which is broadly correlated with anaemia in modern medicine. These are in partial clinical agreement with symptoms of Iron Deficiency Anaemia (IDA), such as pallor, fatigue, and poor appetite.

KEYWORDS: Raktakshaya, Iron Deficiency Anaemia, Rakta Dhatu, Santarpanjanya & Aptarpanjanya pandu, pandu roga.

INTRODUCTION

Iron Deficiency Anaemia (IDA) is one of the most common nutritional disorders globally, especially affecting women and children in developing countries (WHO, 2001).^[1] In India, it remains a major public health concern. According to NFHS-5, around 40% of women and 18.9% of men are moderately anaemic, with higher prevalence in rural areas—58.5% in women and 27.4% in men. States like Chhattisgarh show even higher rates. The main causes include deficiencies of iron, folic acid, vitamin B12, and other nutrients. In Ayurveda, anaemia is understood as *Raktadhatu Kshaya*, and its prevention and management are emphasized through Pathya Ahara (wholesome diet) and Vihara (balanced lifestyle), offering a holistic approach when integrated with modern nutritional science.

Clinical Features of Raktakshaya^[2,3,4]

According to *Acharya Charaka*, symptoms of *Raktakshaya* include *Parusha* (roughness), *Sfutita* (cracking), *Mlana* (weakness), and *Twak Rukshata* (dryness of skin). *Acharya Sushruta* describes it with features like *Shonita Kshaya* (depletion of blood), *Twak Parushya* (skin roughness), *Amla Shita Prarthana* (craving for sour and cold substances), and *Shirasaithilya* (head weakness). *Acharya Vagbhata* mentions *Amla Shishira Priti* (preference for sour and cold), *Shirasaithilya*, and *Rukshata* (dryness) as indicative of *Raktakshaya*. These symptoms reflect qualitative and quantitative depletion of *Rakta Dhatu*.

Pandu Ayurvedic Review^[5,6,7,8,9,10]

The term *Pandu* is derived from the Dhatu “*Padi*” meaning “to destroy” or “to lose,” with the addition of the “*Ku*” *pratyaya*, indicating loss—specifically, the loss of normal skin colour. In *Panduroga*, the skin becomes discoloured, appearing pale like *haridra* (turmeric), *shweta* (white), or *dhusara* (grey). As per *Shabdarnava Kosh*, the colour of *Pandu* resembles the whitish-yellow pollen of the *Ketaki* flower. The disease is defined as an excessive manifestation of paleness throughout the body. *Sushruta* lists synonyms like *Kamala*, *Panaki*, *Lagharaka*, *Alasa*, and *Kumbhahwa*, while the *Vedas* mention names like *Vilohita*, *Halima*, and *Haribha* for similar conditions.

NIDANA^[11,12,13]

Acharya Charak has included the disease *Panduroga* in *Santarpanjanya Vikara* also.

There for considering the both, *Santarpanjaya* & *Aptarpanjanya Panduroga* the *Hetu* can be classified as following.

	SANTARPANJANYA PANDU	APATARPANJANYA PANDU
AAHARAJ	<i>Adhyashana, Ajeernashan, Vishamashana, Ras Pradhanta, Madhur Ras Pradhan, Aahar, Gunapradhanata, Sheet, Guru, Atisnigdha, Picchila, Dravya, Pradhanata, Mash, Pinnyak, Mrid, Anupmansa, Guda & its Products</i>	<i>Laghwashana, Poshan abhavaj Aaharsevan, RasaPradhanta, Amla, Katu, Kshar, Lawan, Guna Pradhanata, Atyushna, Teekshna, Ruksha, Laghu, Dravya -Madya, Pradhanata -Spicy chilly, FoodsMrid</i>
VIHARAJ	<i>Diwaswap, Avyayama, Vegodharan (Mal Mootra), Pratikarma Snehavibhrama, Grahi Chikitsa in Amatisara, Snehatiyoga</i>	<i>Atishrama, Atiadhthagaman, Ativyavaya, Ativyayama, Ratri Jagaran, Vegodharan, Kshudha, Trisha</i>
MANASIK	<i>Irshya, Pradnyaparadha</i>	<i>Kama, Chita, Bhaya, Krodha, Shoka</i>
NIDANARTHAKAR VYADHI	<i>Purishaj Krimi Kaphaj Prameha Medoroga Aampradoshaj Vyadhi</i>	<i>Raktapitta, Raktarsha, Raktapradar, Pleeharoga Kamala, Rakta-Gulma, Jeema Jwara, Rajyakshma, Shosha, Grahani, Aghataj Hetu.</i>

Samanya Roopa (according to Acharya Charaka and Acharya Vagbhata)^[14]

Akshikutashotha (swelling over orbital region), *Aruchi* (anorexia), *Arohanaayasa* (patient feels exhausted on climbing), *Alpawaka* (avoid speaking), *Annadweshha* (aversion towards food), *Bhramanipidita* (giddiness), *Daurbalya* (general weakness), *Gaurva* (heaviness), *Gatrashoola* (body ache), *Shirnaloma* (hair fall), *Hataprabha* (body complexion become greenish), *Karnashveda* (tinnitus), *Shrama* (fatigue), *Jwara* (fever), *Shwasa* (breathlessness), *Kopana* (dislikes cold things), *Nidralu* (feeling of drowsiness), *Shtheevan* (spitting frequently), *Pindikodweshthana* (calf muscle pain), *Kati-uru-paada ruka* (pain and weakness in the lumbar, thighs and feet)

Types of Pandu Roga and Their Symptoms^[15,16,17]

TYPE	CAUSE	SYMPTOMS
VATAJA PANDU	Vata-provoking Ahara (diet) and Vihara (lifestyle) leading to vitiation of Vata dosha.	Krishna-Panduta (black and pale-yellow discoloration), Rukshata (dryness), Aruna-Angatam (redness), Angamarda (body ache), Ruja (pain), Toda (pricking sensation), Kampa (tremor), Parshva-Shiro-Ruja (pain in chest and head), Varchas Shosh (dry stool), Aasyavairasya (distaste), Shopha (edema), Aanaha (constipation), Bala-

		Kshaya (weakness).
PITTAJA PANDU	Pitta-provoking Ahara and Vihara leading to vitiation and accumulation of Pitta dosha.	Pita-Haritabhata (yellow/green discoloration), Jwara (fever), Daha (burning sensation), Trishna (excessive thirst), Murchha (fainting), Pipasa (thirst), Pita Mutra-Shakruta (yellow urine/stool), Sweda (profuse sweating), Sheetakama (desire for cold), Katuka-Kashayata (pungent taste), Ushna-Amla Anupashyata (intolerance to hot/sour food), Vidaaha (burning indigestion), Daurgandhya (foul smell), Daurbalya (weakness), Bhinnavarcha (loose stool/diarrhea).
KAPHAJA PANDU	Kapha-provoking Ahara and Vihara leading to vitiation and accumulation of Kapha dosha.	Gaurava (heaviness), Tandra (drowsiness), Chhardi (vomiting), Shvetavabhasata (whitish complexion), Praseka (excessive salivation), Lomaharsha (goosebumps), Murchha (fainting), Bhrama (giddiness), Klama (mental fatigue), Sada (body looseness), Kasa (cough), Shwasa (breathlessness), Alasya (lethargy), Aruchi (loss of appetite), Vak-swaragraha (speech/voice obstruction), Shukla Mutra-Akshi-Varcha (whiteness in urine, eyes, stool), Shotha (swelling), Madhurasyata (sweet taste).
SANNIPATAJA PANDU	Vitiation of all three Doshas due to intake of Tridoshaja vitiating Ahara and Vihara.	Mixed symptoms of Vataja, Pittaja, and Kaphaja Pandu.
MRIDBHAKSHANA-JANYA PANDU	Eating mud or soil of various tastes (Madhura, Lavana, Kashaya) leads to vitiation of Kapha, Pitta, and Vata respectively.	Bala, Varna, Agni Nash (loss of strength, complexion, and digestion), Shotha in Ganda, Akshi-Kuta, Bhru, Pada, Nabhi, and Medhra (edema on cheeks, eye sockets, eyebrows, feet, navel, and genitals), Krimi in Koshta (intestinal worms), Atisara with Mala, Shonita, and Kapha (diarrhea with blood and mucus).

SAMPRAPTI OF *PANDUROGA*^[18,19]

Panduroga is also described as Santarpanottha Vyadhi according Charak Hence the classification can be given.

Samprapti or Pathogenesis of the disease '*Panduroga*' can be studied according to its origin. Because the Great Acharya Charak has included the disease '*Panduroga*' in Santarpanottha vikara.

Hence the origin of '*Panduroga*' is mainly of two types

1. Santarpanottha *Panduroga*
2. Apatarpanottha *Panduroga*

The following chart gives the general idea of Pathogenesis of Apatarpanottha Santarpanottha *Panduroga*

Here we can only say that there is similarity in Santarpanottha pandu and Kaphaj Pandu and Apatharpanottha Pandu and Vataj and Pittaj *Panduroga*

PANDUROGA AND DHATUKSHAYA

The above discussion indicates that Santarpanottha Panduroga can progress into Apatarpanottha Panduroga over time. In *Charaka Samhita, Chikitsa Sthana* (Panduroga Chikitsa Adhyaya), *Acharya Charaka* mainly describes *Panduroga* from an *Apatarpanottha* (depletion-related) perspective. This suggests that *Dhatukshaya* (tissue depletion) is a significant and often unavoidable factor in the manifestation of *Panduroga*. The signs and symptoms of *Dhatukshaya* relevant to *Panduroga* are elaborated in the section on the *Roopa* (clinical features) of the disease.

Anaemia: A Modern Perspective^[20,21]

Anaemia is a condition that arises when there is an imbalance between the production and loss of red blood cells. It typically occurs due to reduced red blood cell formation or excessive loss. It is characterized by a decrease in haemoglobin levels, red blood cell count, and packed cell volume (PCV), all of which are essential for carrying oxygen throughout the body.

Classification of Anaemia

1. Morphological classification
2. Etiological classification

Morphological Classification

Anaemia can be classified morphologically based on the size and colour of red blood cells. The **cell size** is evaluated using **Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV)**, and the **colour**, which reflects haemoglobin content, is assessed through **Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC)**.

- (1) Normocytic Normochromic, (2) Normocytic Hypochromic, (3) Macrocytic Hypochromic
- (4) Microcytic Hypochromic

Etiological Classification

Anaemia is categorized into several types depending on the underlying cause. Blood loss leads to haemorrhagic anaemia, while red cell breakdown causes haemolytic anaemia. A lack of nutrients like iron or vitamins results in nutritional anaemia. In aplastic anaemia, the bone marrow fails to make enough blood cells, and in chronic diseases, anaemia develops as a complication of long-term illness.

Nutritional Deficiency anaemia

Nutritional deficiency anaemia occurs when the body lacks essential nutrients needed for red blood cell production (erythropoiesis). These nutrients include iron, proteins, and vitamins like B12, folic acid, and vitamin C. Deficiencies in any of these can impair red blood cell formation, leading to various types of anaemia such as iron deficiency anaemia, folic acid deficiency anaemia, vitamin B12 deficiency anaemia, protein deficiency anaemia, and vitamin C-related anaemia.

Iron Deficiency Anaemia

Iron Deficiency Anaemia (IDA) is the most widespread type of nutritional anaemia, resulting from a lack of iron needed for haemoglobin formation. This leads to reduced oxygen delivery to tissues. It affects billions globally, as noted by WHO (2001). IDA is identified when anaemia improves with iron treatment. In this condition, red blood cells are typically **small (microcytic)** and **pale (hypochromic)** under a microscope.

Causes of Iron Deficiency Anaemia

Iron deficiency may occur due to excessive blood loss from injuries, ulcers, or menstruation, as well as from low iron intake in the diet. It can also result from malabsorption issues like celiac disease or persistent diarrhea. Periods of increased demand, such as pregnancy, lactation, or rapid growth, can further contribute to deficiency.

Characteristic Features^[22]

Iron deficiency anaemia is marked by microcytic, hypochromic RBCs, with reduced MCV, MCH, and MCHC.

RBC count may be low or normal. Peripheral smear shows variation in cell size and shape, while the bone marrow reveals normoblastic hyperplasia. Lab findings include low serum iron, high TIBC, and bilirubin below 0.4 mg/dl.

Common signs are brittle nails, koilonychia, smooth red tongue, brittle hair, and dysphagia. Patients may also experience fatigue, breathlessness, chest infections, and neurological symptoms like irritability and poor focus.

Correlation of Types of Pandu with Modern IDA

Type of Pandu	Ayurvedic Description	Possible Modern Correlate
Vataja Pandu	Dryness, weight loss, constipation, blackish discoloration, body pain, insomnia.	IDA with severe fatigue, dry skin, insomnia, and cachexia; seen in chronic undernutrition or malabsorption.
Pittaja Pandu	Yellowish discoloration (like turmeric), burning sensation, excessive thirst, loose stools.	IDA with associated liver dysfunction or hemolytic component; jaundice in differential diagnosis.
Kaphaja Pandu	Heaviness, nausea, lethargy, white discoloration, indigestion, swelling.	IDA with edema, hypoalbuminemia, chronic inflammatory states; poor digestion may reflect malabsorption.
Sannipataja Pandu	Mixed features of Vata, Pitta, Kapha types with severe debility.	Advanced/chronic IDA with systemic symptoms, multi-deficiency state, or mixed pathology.
Mrittika (Mrid) Bhakshana Janya Pandu	Caused by eating clay/mud, associated with distention, indigestion, pallor, weakness	Pica , especially geophagia , commonly seen in IDA. This is a direct correlation in behavior and causality.

CONCLUSION

Raktakshaya and Iron Deficiency Anaemia share similar pathogenesis and symptomatology. An integrative approach combining Ayurvedic dietary principles, herbal formulations, and modern supplements offers a promising avenue for holistic management. Further clinical studies and interdisciplinary research are essential to validate traditional practices in contemporary clinical settings. Raktakshaya, as described in Ayurvedic texts, reflects a deficiency or qualitative derangement of Rakta Dhatu, manifesting through symptoms that closely parallel those of Iron Deficiency Anaemia (IDA) in modern medicine.

The Ayurvedic understanding of Raktakshaya provides a holistic framework that incorporates **Dosha imbalance**, **Agni dysfunction**, and **Dhatu depletion**, while modern medicine attributes IDA primarily to nutritional deficiency, chronic blood loss, or malabsorption. Despite differing paradigms, both systems recognize the systemic impact of blood deficiency, particularly on energy metabolism and organ function.

Raktakshaya, described in Ayurveda as the quantitative or qualitative depletion of Rakta Dhatu, presents clinically as Panduroga when the imbalance becomes significant. The classical texts emphasize that both *Santarpanajanya* (**over-nutrition/excessive intake**) and *Apatarpanajanya* (**under-nutrition/inadequate intake**) states can independently or synergistically lead to Panduta, ultimately manifesting features comparable to **Iron Deficiency Anaemia (IDA)** in modern medicine.

Excessive consumption of guru, snigdha, and madhura ahara, sedentary lifestyle, and metabolic sluggishness contribute to *Santarpanajanya* Panduroga by impairing Agni and hampering proper tissue formation. Conversely, inadequate intake of nutrient-rich foods, chronic illnesses, and poor digestive strength create an *Aptarpanajanya* state, directly reducing the production of Rakta Dhatu. Both pathways converge into hypofunction of Agni, malabsorption, and impaired haemopoiesis — mechanisms that parallel the pathophysiology of IDA.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. (2001). Iron Deficiency Anaemia: Assessment, Prevention and Control.
2. Charak Samhita Pt.Kashinatha Sastri, Dr Gorakha Natha Chaturvedi, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi Sutrasthan Chapter No. 17, shloka no. 65 page 303, reprint 2021.
3. Sushrut Samhita, Kaviraj Ambikadutta shastri sutrasthan, Chaukhamba sanskrit sansthan, Sutrasthan Chapter No.15, Shloka No.13, page 76, Reprint 2019.
4. Ashtang hridayam, Dr Brahmanand Tripathi, Chaukhamba sanskrit sansthan, Sutrasthan ChapterNo. 11 shloka No. 17, page 164 reprint 2012.
5. Shree Taranath BhattAcharya Vachaspatyam Tarakvachaspati, Chaukhamba Sanskrit series Office, 1962; 1: 5
6. Taranath Tarakvachaspati, “Shabdsthome Mahanidhi”, Veedanyantra Press, Culcutta, 1976.
7. Pandey Ajay Kumar, Textbook of Kaya Chikitsa, Vol 2, Chapter 2, Chaukhambha Publications, New Delhi, First Edition, 2019; P-168.
8. Shastri Ambikadatta, Sushruta Samhita, Ayurveda Taatvasandipika Hindi commentary, Vol. II, Chap. 44/15, Chaukhambha Sanskrit sansthan, Varanasi; reprint edition, 2014; p365.
9. Ambika Datta Shastri, Sushrutha Samhita, Uttara tantra, 7th Edition, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Samsthan, Varanasi, 1990; P-286.
10. Rani Khushboo, Gujjarwar Vidula, Gujjarwar Shriniwas; Acta Scientific Nutritional Health, "Mridabhakshanjanya *Pandu*-Review Article, 3; 4; 2019; P-66-69.
11. Agnivesh, *Charaka*, Dridhabala, Pt. Kashinatha Shastri and G. Pandeya; *CharakaSamhita*, Vidhyotini Hindi commentary, *Chikitsa*Sthana, 16/7-9, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Reprint, 2006; p.488.

12. Shastri Ambikadatta, *Sushruta Samhita*, ayurvedatvatvasandipika Hindi commentary, Vol. II, Chap. 44/3, Chaukhamba Sanskrit sansthan, Varanasi; reprint edition, 2014; p-364.
13. Charak Samhita su.23/5 by Vd. Ravidatta tripathi Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthana, Varanasi. Page no. 317.
14. Agnivesh, *Charaka*, Dridhabala, Pt. Kashinatha Shastri and G. Pandeya; *Charaka Samhita*, Vidhyotini Hindi commentary, *Chikitsa* Sthana, 16/13-16, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, reprint, 2006; p.488.
15. Agnivesh, *Charaka*, Dridhabala, Pt. Kashinatha Shastri and G. Pandeya; *Charaka Samhita*, Vidhyotini Hindi commentary, *Chikitsa* Sthana,16/3, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan reprint, 2006; p.486.
16. Agnivesh, *Charaka*, Dridhabala, Pt. Kashinatha Shastri and G. Pandeya; *Charaka Samhita*, Vidhyotini Hindi commentary, *Chikitsa* Sthana,16/17-30, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan reprint, 2006; p.489-90
17. Sushrut Samhita uttar tantra 44/4 published by ayurved tatvasandipika by Ambikadatta shastri Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthana, Varanasi. Page no. 365.
18. *International Journal of Ayurvedic Medicine*, 2015; 6(1): Supplement, 67-83.
19. A systemic review of *Panduroga* w.s.r. To Anaemia Review Article Rakesh D. Pawara^{1*}, Londhe P.D2.
20. Essentials of medical physiology K Sembulingam, Prema sembulingam, Jaypee Brothers medical Publishers chapter 12, page no. 88 reprint 2016.
21. Short textbook of Physiology K.C. Mathur Jaypee Brothers medical Publishers chapter 61, Page no.415-416 reprint 2006.
22. Textbook of physiology Volume 01 A.K. Jain, Arya publishing company Village-Johron Dist- Sirmour (HP), Chapter-08, Page no. 77, 10th edition reprint 2023.